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Investigating the relationship between surface roughness and reflectance properties of building materials

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Abstract. Materials used in the exterior envelope of buildings and open urban surfaces, in general, strongly affect the urban thermal balance, determining the general magnitude of urban overheating. The surface temperature of reflective materials varies as a function of physical and geometrical properties. Quantifying the influence of surface roughness on reflectance properties has crucial relevance since reflectance can significantly affect the reduction of the absorbed solar radiation and, in turn, the energy demand for cooling. Through an experimental and statistical investigation, this research aims to analytically assess the impact of surface roughness on the reflectance and thermal performances of building materials and, in turn, the role that roughness could play towards urban cooling and mitigation. Results show that the surface's different roughness affects the sample's reflectance coefficient, leaving it basically unchanged in the Ultraviolet and Visible ranges but with appreciable differences in the Near-Infrared wavelengths. This outcome confirms the correlation between the surface roughness and the optical and thermal characteristics of the building materials, making evident the importance of the study of superficial topography towards the mitigation of Urban Heat Island phenomena.

1. Introduction

The thermal balance of urban areas is significantly influenced by the choice of materials used in the built environment, such as the exterior envelopes of buildings and other open urban surfaces [1,2]. Due to the absorption of the incident solar radiation, the closely packed buildings and paved surfaces that make up our cities trap and amplify heat, exhibiting a high surface temperature and a high release of sensible heat to the atmosphere, increasing the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon [3,4]. In recent years, scientific researchers have focused on developing mitigation technologies that increase the albedo of cities by reflecting solar radiation [5,6]. For example, Synnefa et al. compared the thermal performances of reflective coatings, showing that they can reduce surface temperature of white concrete tiles even under hot summer conditions [7]. Hernández-Pérez presented a review on the state of the art of the application of reflective materials on buildings' walls and roofs that highlighted a consistent reduction of the daily heat gains and indoor air temperatures, and thus of the daily cooling energy consumptions [8]. However, even highly reflecting white materials can exhibit significant

variability in measured daily surface temperatures, despite being of the same colour [9]. Indeed, the surface temperature of reflective white materials varies as a function of several parameters, such as physical (solar reflectance, emissivity, and thermal capacity) and geometrical (surface roughness, texture, size, and thickness) properties.

In particular, superficial roughness can play a relevant role in determining an object's interaction with the environment, affecting the functional properties of its surfaces [9,10]. Irregularities can affect reflectance in several ways, including scattering light in many directions and altering the average slope of the surface [11]. Generally, a rougher surface will have a lower reflectance than a smoother surface because the roughness causes light to scatter in many directions and eventually causes multiple reflections and, consequently, absorption phenomena [12]. However, the relationship between reflectance and superficial properties is only sometimes straightforward, depending on the specific wavelength and incidence angle of light and the observation scale [13]. Different studies demonstrated the impact of the material's roughness on thermal characteristics, showing that smooth and flat surfaces are of lower surface temperature than similar rough [14]. However, surface roughness is usually considered only from a qualitative and macroscopic point of view. Quantifying the influence of surface roughness on reflectance properties has crucial relevance since reflectance can significantly affect the reduction of the absorbed solar radiation and, in turn, the energy demand for cooling.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Samples production

In this work, eighteen outdoor porcelain stonewares (80 mm × 80 mm × 20(h) mm) for flooring in outdoor environments are selected to investigate a possible correlation between superficial roughness and reflectance properties. Samples' finishes differ in colour and surface texture, guaranteeing heightened anti-slip characteristics thanks to the different superficial bumpinesses. A checkered pattern is produced on the samples dividing the surfaces into four squares (40 mm × 40 mm) and applying opaque spray paint in three different colours (white, grey, black), as shown in Figure 1. In this way, the contribution of colour became uniform between the treated samples, preserving the differences in the surface roughness characteristics.

Figure 1. Samples investigated in the experimental campaign.

2.2. Experimental methodology

2.2.1. Optical characterization. For the first type of analysis, reflectance measurements (300-2500 nm) were performed using a Lambda 1050+ UV/Vis/NIR spectrophotometer equipped with a 150 mm integrating sphere. For each sample, the average value and standard deviation upon three different tests were considered to obtain the material's reflection coefficients and expected deviation, according to the ASTM E903 standard [17].

2.2.2. Surface characterization. Surface roughness was analysed through a Nanovea JR25 optical profilometer designed with Chromatic Confocal technology examining a 1x1 cm area for each sample and colour (acquisition rate 2000 Hz). The instrument was equipped with a Sentech STIL optical pen consisting of a CL4 chromatic lens and an MG35 magnifier with a maximum range of 3.0 mm. According to the evaluation frameworks provided by ISO 25178 standard [18], data obtained were analysed using MountainsMap (Digital Surf) software. The roughness component was isolated by applying S- and L-filters, which eliminated microroughness and waviness, respectively. Height, spatial and hybrid parameters, calculated on the entire surface, were used to quantify surface texture properties and evaluate their functional performances.

2.2.3. Statistical analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a collection of statistical models used to determine whether there are significant differences among groups. ANOVA can be applied to various types of data with different levels of complexity, e.g. Repeated-Measures ANCOVAs compare means across one or more variables based on repeated observations while controlling for up to ten covariate factors. In ANCOVA RM models, the F statistic tests whether the difference in means between the groups is significant after controlling for the effect of one or more continuous covariates. The p-value indicates the probability of obtaining an F value as extreme as the one observed, assuming the null hypothesis is true. A p-value less than the significance level (usually 0.05) indicates a significant difference between the means of the groups after controlling for the effect of the covariates.

In this work, the experimental results of the coloured samples (B, G, W) represented the input for a Repeated-Measures ANCOVA statistical analysis investigating the correlation between the solar reflectance properties and the roughness parameters. Among these parameters, Mean surface roughness (Sa), representing the height difference of each point compared to the arithmetical mean of the surface as defined in Equation 1, was assumed as the predictor variable.

$$Sa = \frac{1}{A} \iint_A |Z(x, y)| dx dy \quad (1)$$

For each sample, reflectance coefficients in the three regions of the solar spectrum (UV, Visible and NIR) were calculated, obtaining the three dependent variables. The other topographic parameters collected by the profilometric analysis (Table 1) were used as the covariates in order to control for the effect of slope and complexity of the surfaces.

Table 1. Surface parameters defined by ISO 25178 [18].

Group	Parameter	Definition	Description
Height	Sa	Mean surface roughness	Arithmetic mean height
	Sq	Root-mean-square height	Standard deviation for the amplitudes
	Ssk	Skewness	Symmetry of the height distribution
	Sku	Kurtosis	Flatness of the height distribution
	Sp	Maximum peak height	Height between highest peak and mean plane.
	Sv	Maximum pit height	Depth between mean plane and deepest valley.

	Sz	Maximum height	Height between highest peak and deepest valley.
Spatial	Ssw	Dominant spatial wavelength	Size of the dominant surface irregularities
Hybrid	Sdq	Root-mean-square slope	Root-mean-square slope of the surface.
	Sdr	Developed interfacial area ratio	Complexity of the surface

3. Results and Discussions

This research seeks to analyse the impact of surface roughness on the reflectance and thermal performance of building materials. By conducting an experimental and statistical investigation, we aim to determine the role that roughness plays in urban cooling and mitigation. Reflectance is influenced by various factors, including colour and surface roughness. Colour relates to which wavelengths of light are absorbed and which are reflected, while surface roughness affects the amount and angle of light reflection. To isolate the contribution of superficial properties, eighteen outdoor porcelain stonewares, differing in colour and surface textures, were painted in three different colours (white, grey, and black).

The application of paint has resulted in significant changes in the optical properties of the samples. The reflectance curves of the untreated samples exhibit high variations in the entire solar spectrum, whereas the curves of the coloured samples tend to be more uniform in the UV and Visible ranges but with appreciable differences in the Near-Infrared wavelengths (Figure 2). In the case of white samples, significant variations can also be seen in the Visible wavelengths, probably due to the higher reflectance values associated with the white colour. For each sample, reflection coefficients in three regions of the solar spectrum were obtained as the average value of three different tests.

Figure 2. Reflectance curves of the investigated samples varying the superficial colour finishing.

A thorough surface characterization was performed using ISO 25178, the first international standard that specifies and measures surface properties in three dimensions. This standard introduced non-contact measurement methods, which allowed us to investigate surface properties of 54 treated samples using optical profilometry, as shown in Figure 3. Our analysis of roughness went beyond simply measuring the distance of points from an ideal smooth surface. We also considered the inclinations and the general complexity of the surface, including curvature, symmetry, and texture.

To accurately describe the surface properties, various classes of parameters were taken into account. Height parameters were used to measure the Z-axis values perpendicular to the mean plane of the surface, including Sq , Ssk , Sku , Sz , and Sa . Spatial parameters were also considered, which use spectral analysis to describe the topographic features and measure the lateral information on the X- and Y- axes (Ssw). Additionally, hybrid parameters measure the information on all three axes (X, Y, and Z), including criteria that depend on both amplitude and spacing, such as slopes and curvatures (Sdq , Sdr).

Figure 3. Surface analysis of 13W sample: a) 3D view, b) false-colour view, c) photo-simulation.

As a simple and widely used parameter to describe the roughness of a surface, the arithmetic mean roughness (Sa) was considered the most representative parameter to be included as the independent variable of the statistical analysis. Since ANCOVA analysis requires categorical data for the independent variables, Sa collected by the profilometer were divided into five classes with increasing value, from 1 (very low roughness) to 5 (very high roughness), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Surface characterization: Mean Surface Roughness of the investigated samples.

Sample	Black		Grey		White	
	Sa [μm]	Class	Sa [μm]	Class	Sa [μm]	Class
1	5,39	2	5,7	2	4,74	1
2	4,73	1	6,22	3	6,17	3
3	6,57	3	7,1	4	6,31	3
4	6,96	3	9,89	5	9,39	5
5	4,22	1	4,67	1	5,58	2
6	8,32	5	5,81	2	6,9	3
7	7,8	4	6,85	3	6,76	3
8	8,37	5	7,44	4	6,72	3
9	7,53	4	7,41	4	13,39	5
10	5,58	2	5,6	2	6,01	3
11	5,39	2	5,58	2	5,56	2
12	5,22	2	6,06	3	5,72	2
13	6,86	3	5,53	2	6,92	3
14	5,33	2	6,72	3	6,19	3
15	5,63	2	7,61	4	8,58	5
16	4,36	1	5,05	2	4,21	1
17	4,8	1	4,66	1	4,92	1
18	5,8	2	5,56	2	5,38	2

After verifying the meeting of assumptions, an RM Ancova analysis has been carried out to investigate the effects of Mean surface roughness on reflectance properties in the solar spectrum, while controlling for other topographic parameters. Table 3 resumes the results of the RM ANCOVA analysis. Mean surface roughness significantly influences the three dependent variables – the variations of reflectance properties in the entire solar spectrum – with a resulting p-value of 0.005, i.e., ten times smaller than the assumed confidence level, after controlling for the effects of covariates.

Table 3. Repeated Measures ANCOVA - Test of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	1691.034	1	1691.34	2.991	.041	.066
Cov - Sq	1184.573	1	1184.573	2.095	.155	.048
Cov - Sku	5066.685	1	5066.685	8.961	.005	.176
Cov - Ssk	700.224	1	700.224	1.238	.272	.029
Cov - Sdq	7278.682	1	7278.682	12.873	<.001	.235
Cov - Sdr	7976.540	1	7976.540	14.108	<.001	.251
Cov - Ssw	4.066	1	4.066	.007	.933	.000
Cov - Sz	354.197	1	354.197	.626	.433	.015
Sa	9830.038	4	2457.510	4.346	.005	.293
Error	23747.181	42	565.409			

Dependent Variables: UV Reflectance, VIS Reflectance, NIR Reflectance

If a covariate in ANCOVA has statistical significance, it suggests a relationship between the covariate and the dependent variable beyond the influence of the independent variable(s) studied. In this analysis, three covariates showed a significant effect on the dependent variable: (i) *Sku* - Kurtosis

of the height distribution, qualifying the flatness of the surface (Sig. = 0.005); (ii) Sdq - Root-mean-square slope of the surface (Sig. < 0.001); and (iii) Sdr - Developed interfacial area ratio, indicating the complexity of the surface respect to a projected horizontal surface (Sig. < 0.001). Conversely, other topographic parameters did not demonstrate any additional variance in the dependent variable beyond what was already explained by the predictor variable.

Estimated Marginal Means (EMMs) are statistical outputs in ANCOVA repeated measures that evaluate the mean response of each condition while accounting for the covariates' influences. Visual representations of EMMs aid the interpretation of the results by providing a clearer picture of the differences between the groups when comparing the effects of different treatments. Figure 4 shows EMMs of Reflectance in the entire solar spectrum for each class of Sa while considering covariates at their mean values. The mean response in reflectance tends to decrease as the mean surface roughness grows. This result is consistent with the literature [19], confirming that surface roughness can negatively influence reflectance properties.

Figure 4. Estimated marginal means of Reflectance. Covariates are considered at their mean values.

4. Conclusions

This study delved into the connection between surface roughness and reflectance properties of building materials. Samples, differing in colour and surface textures, were painted in three different colours to isolate the contribution of superficial properties. Results of an RM ANCOVA statistical analysis showed that mean surface roughness significantly influences the sample's reflectance coefficients. Indeed, a rougher surface was associated with minor reflectance properties, with appreciable differences in the Near-Infrared wavelengths. On the other hand, UV reflectance remained more uniform, while noticeable variations could be seen in the Visible wavelengths for white samples. This outcome confirms the correlation between the surface roughness and the optical and thermal characteristics of the building materials, making evident the importance of the study of superficial topography towards the reduction of solar radiation absorption and the mitigation of UHI phenomena. Moreover, the analysis suggested that there is a relationship between other surface parameters, acting as covariates, and the dependent variables, i.e. the reflectance coefficients. This relationship needs to be further examined.

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